

Tourism Promotion and Development in Tamil Nadu: A Study

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A B S T R A C T

Tourism plays a pivotal role in promoting goodwill among the people and thereby fostering socio-economic development of the country. It is driven by the natural urge of very human being for new experiences, and the desire to be both educated and entertained. The motivations for tourism also include religious and business interests. The basic human thrust for new experience and knowledge has become stronger, as communication barriers are getting overcome by technological advances. Tourism as an industry helps to earn huge foreign exchange reserves and creates direct and indirect employment opportunities to a very large section of the society. It is necessary to make a distinction between different types of tourism for an analytical purpose. For instance, tourism is usually classified into two broad categories; international tourism and domestic tourism defined in terms of territorial boundary of the permanent residence of the tourist. Tourism is the vital breath in the human activity while making a prolonged journey from place to place. It is a human desire to make a round of the places of interest religious spiritual, Natural, beautiful places, monuments, ancient cities, historical sites, pilgrimage centre tourism.

Key words: Tourism, foreign exchange reserves, ancient cities, pilgrimage centre.

Introduction

Tourism has been defined as a multi-faceted phenomenon of societies all over the world. It is driven by the natural urge of every human being for new experience, and the desire to be both educated and entertained. The motivations for tourism also include religious and business interests. The basic human thrust for new experience and knowledge has become stronger, as communication barriers are getting overcome knowledge has become stronger, as communication barriers are getting overcome by technological advances. Progress in air transport and development of tourist facilities has encouraged people to venture beyond the boundaries.¹

Tourism has been a major social phenomenon of societies all over the world. It is driven by the natural urge of very human being for new experiences, and the desire to be both educated and entertained. The motivations for tourism also include religious and business interests. The basic human thrust for new experience and knowledge has become stronger, as communication barriers are getting overcome by technological advances. Progresses in air transport and development of tourist facilities have encouraged people to venture beyond the boundaries.²

Tourism is the vital breath in the human activity while making a prolonged journey from place to place. It is a human desire to make a round of the places of interest religious spiritual, Natural, beautiful places, monuments, ancient cities, historical sites, pilgrimage centre tourism. The importance of Tourism as an instrument of economic development and employment generation, particularly in remote and backward areas, has been well recognized the world over. It is a large service industry globally in terms of gross revenue as well as foreign exchange earnings. Tourism is recognized as a powerful engine for economic of tourism to the country's GDP and the total job was 5.92 per cent and 9.24 per cent respectively during 2011-12.³

Formation of Tourism in India

Tourism in India has emerged from being a relatively insignificant sector to a fast-growing industry making significant contribution to the national economy. The basic materials for Tourism Industry – culture, heritage, natural vegetation, beaches, parks, monuments, sculptures etc – all tangible and immovable – which India possesses abundantly

can be exploited for the betterment of her economy¹⁴. The first organised effort to promote tourism in India was made in the year 1945. A committee was set up by the Government of India under the chairmanship of Sir John Sergeant. Besides other things, the committee recommended a separate tourist organisation to be set up at the centre with the regional offices in metropolitan tourist organisation to be set up at the centre with the regional offices in metropolitan cities of Bombay, Delhi, Calcutta and Madras¹⁵.

In 1949, there was only a “Tourist Traffic Branch” under the Ministry of Transport. In March 1958, a separate Department of Tourism was established in place of ‘Tourist traffic branch’ under the Ministry of Transport and Communications.⁴ In January 1966, Ministry of Transport and Aviation was formed with two Departments viz., Department of Aviation and Department of Transport, Shipping and Tourism. In September, 1966 “Tourism” portion was transferred to the Department of Aviation and the department was renamed as the Department of Aviation and Tourism. As far as India is concerned the subject of tourism comes under both Union and states. Vital areas of foreign travel like visa, immigration, maintaining offices at abroad comes under Union government and the other vital aspects like infrastructure and maintenance of tourist places are under the jurisdiction of states.⁵

There was a decline in tourist traffic to India from 1,39,804 in 1961 to 1,34,036 in 1962. This prompted the Government to appoint an *ad hoc* committee on Tourism in March, 1963, under the chairmanship of L.K. Jha. Recommendations made by the L.K. Jha Committee included, opening of additional tourist offices abroad, grant of landing permits on arrival of tourists coming without Visa for more than seventy-two hours, setting up of three governments’ corporations to develop Hotel, Transportation and Entertainment facilities.⁶ The Jha Committee also recommended building 5500 additional hotel rooms within the next five years. Official approval of restaurants, shops, guides; provision of shopping , entertainment facilities and improvement of facilities at airports; provision of adequate facilities by Indian Airlines; import of cars integrated development of a few selected tourist centres; increase tourist publicity; training of immigration and customer, staff; stoppage of leakage of foreign exchange; and establishment of a standing committee of main departments of the government dealing with Tourism for reviewing inadequacies.⁷

In 1965, a high-level coordination committee was appointed to implement the recommendations of the Jha Committee. Three new institutions were established namely, the

India Tourism Corporation Limited, the Hotel Corporation of India Limited and the India Tourism Transport Undertaking Limited. The three corporations did not seem to be working well and therefore, amalgamated into one corporation with effect from 1st October 1966, and the new corporation was called as India Tourism Development Corporation Ltd.⁸ In March 1967, the department was converted into the Ministry of Tourism and Civil Aviation with two Departments viz., Department of Tourism and the Department of Civil Aviation. In September 1982, Tourism and Civil Aviation was split into ministries viz., Ministry of Tourism and Ministry of Civil Aviation. In February 1983, the two Ministries were again declared as departments and in the Ministry of Tourism and Civil Aviation. In September 1985, the Department of Tourism was attached with the Department of Parliamentary affairs in the Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs and Tourism. In May 1986, “Tourism was declared as an independent Ministry.”⁹ In June 1988, there was again a re-union of the Ministry of Tourism with the Ministry of Civil Aviation and they formed the Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism. On 26th December 1989, once again, Tourism was bifurcated into two separate ministries, the Ministries were once again declared as two departments in the Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism in June 1991, immediately after the then Prime Minister Narasimha Rao’s Ministry was constituted. Despite terrorist threats in Punjab and Kashmir, the Ayodhya incidents and the consequent communal riots, a strike in Indian Airlines and Air India, the serial bomb blasts in Bombay, the earthquake in Maharashtra, tourists from Europe, the U.S.A., and the Far East still prefer India and found it safer.¹⁰

Tourist Arrivals to India

The share of India in International tourist arrivals progressively increased from 2.2 per cent in 2009 to 5.94 per cent in 2013.¹¹ Foreign Tourist Arrivals (FTAs) rose from 5.11 million in 2009 to 6.29 million in 2013. Tourism makes a significant contribution to India’s foreign exchange earnings, which grew from US\$ 11.39 billion (Rs.54960 crores) in 2009 to US\$ 16.56 billion (Rs.77591 crores) in 2013. The share of India in world earnings from Tourism registered an increase from 4.7 per cent in 2009 to 14.0 per cent in 2013.¹² The number of Domestic tourists in India rose from 668.03 million in 2009 to 850.86 million in 2011. Tourism sector accounts for 2.4% of total direct employment. Including estimated indirect employment its share will raise to 6% of overall employment. India among top 5 medical tourism hotspot in the world.¹³ The Ministry of Tourism started a new campaign for the safety of women titled - “I respect women”.¹⁴

Tourism in Tamil Nadu

The state of Tamil Nadu gained prominence as an important tourist destination when the Union government decided to promote South India as a major tourist destination centre. Accordingly, steps were initiated to market the South tourist spots, including the temples, not as individual places but as a whole. In other words, in September 1977, about sixty travel writers visited South India under “Destination South India” programme. Its aim to achieve the No. 1 position in tourist arrivals in Tamil Nadu.¹⁵

Tourist Arrivals to Tamil Nadu

In the year 2011, 1400.59 lakhs tourists visited Tamil Nadu. During the year 2012, tourist arrival was 1876.99 lakhs.

- ✓ Foreign Tourist Arrivals: Tamil Nadu stands **SECOND** Next to Maharashtra
- ✓ Domestic Tourist Arrivals: Tamil Nadu stands **THIRD Next** to Andhra Pradesh And Uttar Pradesh

Mission

- ✓ Promoting Tamil Nadu as an attractive tourist destination at the international level
- ✓ Preserving the rich cultural heritage and monuments of architectural splendour and exploit the Tourism potential of these monuments
- ✓ Positioning Tamil Nadu as a visible global brand in Tourism
- ✓ Enhancing Tamil Nadu Tourism’s market within India

Objectives

1. To strengthen the existing tourism infrastructure in the State.
2. To identify the gaps in tourism infrastructure and formulate development schemes.
3. To exploit the tremendous unexploited potential for the promotion of Tourism.
4. To provide world class services for the tourists visiting the State.¹⁶

Development Strategies

- ✓ Identifying and developing lesser-known tourist centres to decongest the popular destinations
- ✓ Creating employment opportunities through tourism growth
- ✓ Capacity Development Programs for service providers including the Staff of the Tourism Department
- ✓ Accrediting tourist guides; displaying schedule of rates on the Web Site of Tamil Nadu Tourism Development Corporation; training them in collaboration with other departments like Museums, Archaeology and Hindu Religious and Charitable Endowments Department
- ✓ Improving the tourist infrastructure facilities at the existing tourist centres, through Government and private sector investments
- ✓ To provide ramp facilities wherever possible for differently-abled and elders at the tourist centres
- ✓ To enhance the quality of experience by ensuring cleanliness through waste management and awareness campaigns at the tourist destinations.
- ✓ Provision of well-maintained toilets of acceptable standards.
- ✓ Provision of waiting shelters and infrastructure at temples, tourist places.
- ✓ Developing Tamil Nadu as a MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conventions and Exhibitions) destination to attract group tourists.¹⁷

New Tourism Policy in Tamil Nadu

The “Vision Tamil Nadu – 2023” released by the hon’ble Chief minister envisages a major role for Tourism in the overall development of the state.¹⁸ To achieve the targets set in the Vision document, a new Tourism Policy is being formulated. The new Tourism Policy aims to attract more high spending tourists and also investments in tourism and hospitality related infrastructure. The Policy will also ensure employment for skilled and unskilled persons, besides inclusive development for the local people. The foreign tourist arrivals targeted for 2023 is 15 million tourists from the present 3.60 million tourists. The

infrastructure development schemes and marketing plans of this Department is aimed at achieving the long term goals set by the Vision Tamil Nadu - 2023.¹⁹ A study on the tourism potential of Tamil Nadu by the Rail India Technical and Economic Survey (RITES), a Government of India Public Sector Undertaking, (1991) examined the then existing tourism infrastructure and to project the future demand, so as to provide adequate facilities to the tourists.

Conclusion

Tourism is a basic and the most desirable human activity, deserving the praise and encouragement of all people and government. At present, tourism is one of the largest export industries in the world in terms of turnover and employment. Basically, tourism ensures the greatest happiness and pleasure of the greatest number. It confers socio-economic, cultural, financial and other benefits on the countries and the people as well. As such, developing countries have been vying with each other to attract tourist both domestic and foreign, in leaps and bounds. Indian is no exception. She has many tourism potentials to cash in on. Tourism in Indian is a growing industry and the country has taken various measures to fully exploit it.

The Department of Tourism has been formulating and implementing various schemes for the promotion of tourism and the development of tourism infrastructure in the country. These relate to domestic or culture; tourism, development of supplementary accommodation and circuits, promotion of fairs and festivals, granting loans to the State Governments and the Union territories, granting loans with concessions to hotels and the tourism transport operators. It is an important floral industry. Almost the entire world has been attracted by the tourism phenomenon.²⁰

Endnotes:

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